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A Hoard from the Wars of the Diadochi in the Kamun Cave, Western Galilee

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Abstract

In 2015 two cavers reported to the Israel Antiquities Authority a hoard of ancient silver jewelry and two coins from an inner chamber of the ‘Kamun Cave’, a large karst cave in Western Galilee. A comprehensive archaeological survey followed, on behalf of the Israel Antiquities Authority, in cooperation with Hebrew University’s Cave Research Center. This article discusses the two coins from the hoard, and another (bronze) coin found in the survey, and establishes their dates. From the hoard’s estimated burial date it is suggested that the cave served as a refuge for people fleeing from the fighting in the region during the Diadochi period.

INTRODUCTION

The ‘Kamun Cave’ is a large karstic cave (total length of 225 m) located at an altitude of 378 m. above sea level on the Kamun ridge in Western Galilee. The hidden and difficult-to-access entrance to the cave is located in the center of a broad hill, on a local ridgeline between Naḥal Shazur and Naḥal Tzuf. The Beit Ha-Qerem Valley located to the north and at the foot of the hill where the cave is located, allows relatively easy access to the Phoenician port city of ‘Akko (Fig. 1).

In early March 2015 two cavers who visited the Kamun Cave reported to the Antiquities Theft Prevention Unit of the Israel Antiquities Authority the discovery of an ancient hoard composed of silver jewelry and coins inside one of the inner halls of the cave. Following this report, a comprehensive archaeological survey was conducted in the cave on behalf of the Israel Antiquities Authority and in cooperation with the Cave Research Center at the Hebrew University.¹

1 The survey was directed by Klein on behalf of the Israel Antiquities Authority. We thank the cavers Reuven and Chen Zakai for discovering the hoard and reporting on it to the Israel Antiquities Authority. We would also like to thank the participants of the survey: Boaz Langford, Micka Ullman, Roi Porat, Amos Frumkin, Nir Distelfeld, Ira Horowitz, Amir Ganor, Gideon Goldenberg, Ronit Lupu, Daniel Ben-Tov, Yinon Shvitiel, Moran Plitvinski, Tehila Eliasi, Matan Avital and the late Ahikam Amihai. Thanks also to the workers of the Artifacts Treatment, Conservation and Laboratories Department headed by Zvi Greenhut: Raisa Vinitzky, Josef Bukengolts, Naama

Fig. 1. Plan of the Kamun Cave (Drawing: Matan Avital, Ahikam Amihai, Boaz Langford, Micka Ullman)

During the survey various artifacts were collected (to be published in the near future), including many fragments of Galilean Coarse Ware storage jars gathered in all parts of the central chamber (Fig. 2; Areas C and D). This pottery attests that the main human activity took place in this hall. The finds indicate that use of the Kamun Cave dates to the beginning of the Hellenistic period, following a minor presence there during the Iron Age.

Fig. 2. Two broken parts of Galilean Coarse Ware storage jar (Photo: Eitan Klein)

This article will present and discuss the coins that were part of the hoard, and another coin uncovered in the survey. On the basis of the surmised deposition date of the hoard we will suggest that the cave served as a refuge for a group of people who fled from the fighting in the region during the Wars of the Diadochi.

LOCATION AND DESCRIPTION OF THE HOARD

The hoard was found lying on a rock inside a natural horizontal crevice (Locus 102) on the southern part of a difficult-to-access eastern wing of the cave (Area E). The hoard (Fig. 3) included two round silver earrings, three boat-shaped silver earrings, two silver rings, five silver bracelets, a stone stamp and a glass seal; objects of this kind were all in frequent use during the late Persian period, during the fifth and fourth centuries BCE. The closest parallels to this jewelry come from burial caves dating to this period at Kāmid el-Lōz in Lebanon (Poppa 1978; approximately 90 km from the Kamun Cave).

Sukenik, Irena Lidsky-Reznikov and Clara Amit. The article was written during a stay at the Oxford Centre for Hebrew and Jewish Studies.

Fig. 3. The Kamun Cave jewelry and coin hoard (Photo: Clara Amit)

Together with the jewelry, two *tetradrachms* minted in the name of Alexander the Great were found (Cat. Nos. 1 and 2; Figs. 4:1 and 4:2). Traces of warp and woof wool fabric were found on the jewelry, suggesting that the hoard was originally placed inside of textile. One bronze coin was also found during the survey in the central chamber of the cave (Area C; Cat. No. 3; Fig. 4:3) and, although not part of the hoard, it will also be discussed here.

Fig. 4. Coins from the Kamun Cave archaeological survey (Photos: Clara Amit)

CATALOGUE

1. Reg. No. 1003, L102. IAA 161145.
 Alexander the Great, Sardis, 319–315 BCE (Price) or 310–302 BCE (Thompson).

Obv.: Beardless head of Heracles r. wearing lion skin; border of dots.

Rev.: Zeus seated l. on throne, holding eagle in r. hand and scepter in l.; in l. field: M ; on r., downwards: $\text{A}\Lambda\text{E}\Xi\text{A}\text{N}\Delta\text{P}\text{O}\text{Y}$; border of dots.

\mathcal{R} *tetradrachm*, \uparrow , 17.13 g, 24×26 mm.

Price 1991:334, No. 2664; Thompson 1983:35–36, Series XIX.

2. Reg. No. 1002, L102. IAA 161146.

Alexander the Great, ‘Babylon’, 311–305 BCE (Price) or 313/2–311/10 BCE (Waggoner).

Obv.: Beardless head of Heracles r. wearing lion skin; border of dots.

Rev.: Zeus seated l. on throne, holding eagle in r. hand and scepter in l.; in l. field: M ; beneath throne: M ; on r., downwards: $\text{A}\Lambda\text{E}\Xi\text{A}\text{N}\Delta\text{P}\text{O}[\text{Y}]$; below throne: $\text{B}\Lambda\text{S}\text{I}\Lambda\text{E}[\text{Q}\Sigma]$; border of dots.

\mathcal{R} *tetradrachm*, \downarrow , 17.14 g, 26×27 mm.

Price 1991:476, No. 3746; Waggoner 1968:185, Issue VIII, series 3.

3. Reg. No. 1013, L100. IAA 161144.

Alexander the Great, Caunos, c. 320 BCE.

Obv.: Shield; border with dots.

Rev.: Helmet; in fields: ear of corn (?) – K

\mathcal{A} , 3.21 g, 14 mm.

Price 1991:275, No. 2072.

Cat. No. 1

The chronology of the Sardian mint in the last two decades of the fourth century is exceedingly vexing. On the one hand, a group of issues linked to others struck in the name of Philip III hold one part of the coinage up before his death in late 317 BCE. On the other hand, the last Alexandrine issues of the mint are linked to issues of Lysimachus and seem to belong in the period immediately after the Battle of Ipsos in 301 BCE. Both Price and Thompson were inclined to suggest a significant gap in production at Sardis between these two groups. For Price the gap was between c. 315 and 301 BCE, and occurred between his numbers 3687 and 2689. For Thompson it occurred between 319/8 and 310 BCE and Price nos. 2641 and 2642 (her series XV and XVI). According to Price’s chronology *Cat. No. 1* would fall approximately between 319 and 315 BCE, Thompson calculated it between c. 310 and 302 BCE, but the issue is not die- or control-linked to the earlier or the later series. There is one important piece of hoard evidence in the form of the ‘Aleppo’ 1893 hoard (*IGCH*:208, No. 1516).² Thompson (1983:42) noted that this hoard contained 27 coins of her Series XVI–XIX “in fine to mint

² For the composition and likely date of this hoard see Duyrat 2005:133.

condition according to Newell's notes". The latest dated coins in the hoard are those of Tyre (Ake), which run down to year 10 (306/5 BCE), suggesting a date of deposit for the Aleppo hoard of *c.* 306–300 BCE. This in turn suggests that Thompson's Series XIX, and thus our coin, was struck within *c.* 310–300 BCE, and that Thompson's date is to be preferred. The Kamun Cave hoard coin appears to have seen very little wear, which perhaps suggests a burial date for the hoard not long after the coin was struck, approximately 310–295 BCE.

Cat. No. 2

The chronology of the mint of Babylon has been no less debated than that of Sardis. Cat. No. 2 is a minor variant of Price 3746 (the monogram in left field appears to have no horizontal element). Price dated the issues with control MI to the period after Antigonos' rule in Mesopotamia, which ended in 311 BCE, but offered no clear rationale for his range of 311–305 BCE. Waggoner (1968:185) arrived at her more precise dates of 313/2–311/10 BCE on the basis of the inclusion of a small number of coins of her Issue VIII, series 3 (to which her series 2 is die linked, and from which it should probably not be chronologically distinguished) as the latest Babylonian coins in the Abu Hommos 1919 hoard (*IGCH:234*, No. 1667). She calculated the date of deposit of this hoard as *c.* 311 BCE on the basis of its Ptolemaic contents: It contained early reduced-weight coins of Ptolemy I, which according to Newell had been introduced *c.* 312 BCE. However, as Lorber (2012) has now argued, the date of this weight reduction is more likely to be *c.* 305 BCE. The Abu Hommos hoard's date must be lowered accordingly, and so must the date of its Babylonian contents. On this basis, the *terminus ante quem* for the striking of the Kamun Cave coin becomes *c.* 305 BCE. Price's chronology for this issue, therefore appears to be correct. Given that our specimen has seen virtually no wear, it suggests a date of deposit for the Kamun Cave hoard between approximately 311 and 300 BCE.

Cat. No. 3

The bronze coin discovered as a single find in the central chamber of the cave is of a type assigned by Price to 'Miletus or Mylasa', with a date of *c.* 320 BCE. The mint attribution was strongly challenged by Ashton (2004), who pointed out on the basis of findspots that a mint in southwestern Asia Minor is far more likely. He suggested Caunos in Caria. The date assigned by Price for this coin's production is approximate, and the condition of our specimen suggests that it has seen some wear. It was probably lost in the last two decades of the fourth century, but no further precision is possible.

HISTORICAL CIRCUMSTANCES

The finds discovered in the cave indicate intensive human activity only during one major period, at the beginning of the Hellenistic period. The massive use of Galilean Coarse Ware storage jars suggests that the refugees who fled to the cave belonged to the Autochthonic/ Semitic population who lived in the Galilee during this period (Frankel et al. 2001:61–62). It is possible that the refugees originated from Ḥorbat Kamun, c. 2.5 km east of the cave and at the top of the Kamun ridge, where a recently published clay *mortarium* from the Persian period or the beginning of the Hellenistic period was found, attesting to a settlement in those periods at the site (Hartal 2012:48–46, Fig. 2:17), or they may have originated from other settlements that existed in the nearby area during this period.

As detailed above, the silver jewelry hoard with two *tetradrachms* in the name of Alexander the Great was deposited in the eastern wing (Area E) of the cave. The bronze coin found in the central chamber, dating back to about 320 BCE, close to the time when the bundle of jewelry and coins was concealed, suggests that individuals in the central hall (Area C) hid their precious possessions in this hidden and difficult-to-access wing. As noted in the commentary, consideration of the production dates and comparative freshness of the two coins from the hoard (Figs. 4:1 and 4:2) suggest that the hoard was concealed most probably between 310 and 300 BCE.

There are several possibilities regarding the date and reason for the refugees' flight to the cave. Diodorus Siculus described how Ptolemy I, after his victory over Demetrius Poliorcetes in 312 BCE at Gaza, continued with his army to fight against the cities of Phoenicia:

Ptolemy sent the captured soldiers off into Egypt, ordering them to be distributed among the nomes; but he himself, after giving a magnificent burial to all those of his own men who had died in the battle, went with his forces against the cities of Phoenicia, besieging some of them and winning others by persuasion (Diod. Sic. 19:85.4).³

Diodorus went on to note that Ptolemy held these cities for a while but later, when Antigonos Monophthalmus arrived in the area, Ptolemy withdrew from Phoenicia back to Egypt, destroying a number of coastal cities, including 'Akko:

Deciding therefore, to leave Syria, he razed the most noteworthy of the cities that he had captured: Ake in Phoenician Syria, and Ioppe, Samaria,

3 ὁ δὲ Πτολεμαῖος τοὺς μὲν ἄλόντας στρατιώτας ἀποστείλας εἰς Αἴγυπτον προσέταξεν ἐπὶ τὰς νομαρχίας διελεῖν, αὐτὸς δὲ θάψας τῶν ἰδίων τοὺς ἐν τῇ μάχῃ τελευτήσαντας ἅπαντας μεγαλοπρεπῶς μετὰ τῆς δυνάμεως ἐπήει τῶν κατὰ Φοινίκην πόλεων τὰς μὲν πολιορκῶν, τὰς δὲ πειθοῖ προσαγόμενος.

and Gaza in Syria; then he himself, taking the army and what of the booty it was possible to drive or carry, returned into Egypt (Diod. Sic, 19:3.7).⁴

It is now accepted that the Battle of Gaza took place in the winter of 312/1 BCE (Errington 1977:496–500; Billows 1997:134, No. 67), and therefore most scholars have assigned both Ptolemy's military conquests in Phoenicia and the destruction of the city of 'Akko as part of his retreat to Egypt to 311 BCE (Billows 1997:129; Boiy 2007:145–146; Meeus 2012:89–92). This is probably too early to be the historical circumstance within which the Kamun Cave hoard was buried.

A more plausible candidate for the time when the cave might have been used for refuge is year 306 BCE. During this year Antigonos and Demetrius launched their campaign against Egypt itself. Diodorus mentioned that the great army assembled for battle advanced through the cities of Phoenicia and the coastal plain to the south:

He had decided to make a campaign against Egypt. So he himself took command of the land army and advanced through Coele Syria with more than eighty thousand foot soldiers, about eight thousand horsemen, and eighty-three elephants. Giving the fleet to Demetrius, he ordered him to follow along the coast in contact with the army as it advanced.... (Diod. Sic. 20:73.1–2).⁵

Although no battles took place in Palestine, it is clear that the region saw massive troop movements in this campaign.

Another candidate for the reason and date of refuge in the cave are the governmental changes that took place in Palestine in 301 BCE, when Ptolemy I gained control of the area, as described by Diodorus:

As for Seleucus, after the partition of the Kingdom of Antigonos, he took his army and went to Phoenicia, where, in accordance with the terms of the agreement, he endeavoured to appropriate Coele Syria. But Ptolemy had already occupied the cities of that region.... (Diod. Sic. 21:1.5).⁶

But in this case the sources do not report whether this takeover was accompanied by military activity.

4 διὸ καὶ κρίνας ἐκλίπειν τὴν Συρίαν κατέσκαψε τὰς ἀξιολογωτάτας τῶν κεκρατημένων πόλεων, Ἄκην μὲν τῆς Φοινίκης Συρίας, Ἰόππην δὲ καὶ Σαμάρειαν καὶ Γάζαν τῆς Συρίας, αὐτὸς δὲ τὴν δύναμιν ἀναλαβὼν καὶ τῶν χρημάτων ὅσα δυνατὸν ἦν ἄγειν ἢ φέρειν ἐπανῆλθεν εἰς Αἴγυπτον.

5 ἔκρινε δὲ στρατεύειν ἐπὶ τὴν Αἴγυπτον. αὐτὸς μὲν οὖν τοῦ πεζοῦ στρατεύματος ἀφηγούμενος προῆγε διὰ τῆς Κοίλης Συρίας, ἔχων πεζοὺς μὲν πλείους τῶν ὀκτακισμυρίων, ἵππεῖς δὲ περὶ ὀκτακισχιλίους, ἐλέφαντας δὲ τρισὶ πλείους τῶν ὀγδοήκοντα· τῷ δὲ Δημητρίῳ παραδοὺς τὸν στόλον συνέταξε συμπαραπλεῖν ἅμα πορευομένη τῇ δυνάμει....

6 Ὅτι Σέλευκος μετὰ τὴν διαίρεσιν τῆς Ἀντιγόνου βασιλείας ἀναλαβὼν τὴν δύναμιν παρεγένετο εἰς Φοινίκην καὶ ἐπεχείρησε κατὰ τὰς γενομένας συνθήκας τὴν Κοίλην Συρίαν ἰδιοποιεῖσθαι. προκατειληφότος δὲ τὰς ἐν αὐτῇ πόλεις Πτολεμαίου....

A number of coin hoards dating to the last two decades of the fourth century BCE are known from Palestine and the surrounding area, which clearly attest to the lack of stability in the region during the Wars of the Diadochi. The data was most recently been surveyed by Duyrat (2016) who listed the following hoards from the immediate region:⁷

91. Tel Michal 1977–1980 (*CH* 10:33, No. 256). After 325–320 BCE.⁸ Kindler 1989.

99. Kirbet el-Kerak 1936 (*IGCH*:207, No. 1510 = *CH* 8:67, No. 587 = *CH* 9:47, No. 462). *c.* 323–320 BCE. Baramki 1945.

105. Tel Tsippor 1960 (*IGCH*:207, No. 1514). *c.* 311–305 BCE.⁹ Rahmani 1966.

109. Jericho 1991 (*CH* 8: 24, No. 215). *c.* 305 BCE.

111. Ashkelon 1990 (*CH* 8:25, No. 220). *c.* 305–290 BCE.

The evidence for the deposit of Alexanders in Syrian hoards was analyzed by Duyrat (2011), where she noted a pronounced spike in hoard deposition with the arrival of Alexander the Great, continuing into the early 320s, after which

les chiffres restent relativement élevés jusqu'à 295, reflétant l'insécurité persistante en Syrie durant la conquête les troupes fraîches rejoignant l'armée et les vétérans de retour vers leurs foyers sont amenés à traverser la région s'ils ne sont pas dirigés vers l'Asie Mineure – puis durant les luttes entre les Diadoques qui conduisent la région à passer sous différentes autorités, imposées souvent les armes à la main.¹⁰

7 We provide the numbering of the hoards from Duyrat's catalogue (pp. 75–85). For a map of finds of this period see p. 548, Map 7. Numerous other hoards without firm findspots may belong in this list too.

8 For a date in 311 BCE following the withdrawal of Ptolemy I back to Egypt from the Phoenician coast see Ariel 2006:80.

9 Rahmani determined that the coins were minted between 317 and 312 BCE and only one coin from the mint of Ecbatana was minted between 311–303 BCE. Therefore he set the date of the entire hoard for 311 BCE or later (Rahmani 1966). In fact the issue of Ecbatana present is one of the very earliest produced by the mint (Price 1991:491, No. 3889), which probably began to strike *c.* 311 BCE. 311 BCE is thus the *terminus post quem* for deposit of Tel Tsippor. That it is not likely to have been buried much later that this is suggested by the issues of Tyre ('Ake') present. These run down to Year 33 (Price 1991:413, No. 3286: 314/3 BCE), but probably not much later (2 coins have illegible dates and are struck from obverse dies unknown to Newell). The Babylonian issues run down to Issue VIII series 2 and 3 (Price 1991:473–477, No. 3704 [7], 3708 [1], 3722 [1], 3726 [1], 2746 [12], 3751 [2]), which were present, as we have noted, in the Abu Hommos hoard, deposited *c.* 305 BCE. Therefore both the Tell Tsippor and 'Kamun Cave' hoards seem to contain issues down to *c.* 305 BCE.

10 Duyrat 2011:420–421, Figs. 1 and 2 and p. 422 (quotation).

In any case, the finds discovered in the Kamun Cave add yet more evidence for the political instability which prevailed in the region during the Wars of the Diadochi.

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ABBREVIATIONS

- AJC* Y. Meshorer. *Ancient Jewish Coinage*. Dix Hills, NY 1982
- AJN* *American Journal of Numismatics*
- BMC* e.g., *BMC Arab.*: G.F. Hill. *Catalogue of the Greek Coins of Arabia, Mesopotamia, and Persia*. London 1922
- BMCO* e.g., *BMCO 1*: S. Lane-Poole. *The Coins of the Eastern Khaleefehs in the British Museum. Catalogue of the Oriental Coins in the British Museum 1*. London 1875
- CH* *Coin Hoards*
- CHL* Y. Meshorer, G. Bijovsky and W. Fischer-Bossert. *Coins of the Holy Land: The Abraham and Marian Sofaer Collection at the American Numismatic Society and the Israel Museum*. Ed. by D. Hendin and A. Meadows. New York 2013
- CIL* *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum*
- CNP* e.g., L. Kadman. *The Coins of Akko Ptolemis* (Corpus Nummorum Palaestinensium IV). Jerusalem 1961
- CRE* e.g., H. Mattingly. *The Coins of the Roman Empire in the British Museum I. Augustus to Vitellius*. London 1923
- DOC* e.g., P. Grierson. *Catalogue of the Byzantine Coins in the Dumbarton Oaks Collection and in the Whittemore Collection 3. Leo III to Nicephorus III 717–1081*. Washington, D.C. 1973
- IEJ* *Israel Exploration Journal*
- IG* *Inscriptiones Graecae*
- IGCH* M. Thompson, O. Mørkholm and C.M. Kraay. *An Inventory of Greek Coin Hoards*. New York 1973
- INJ* *Israel Numismatic Journal*
- INR* *Israel Numismatic Research*
- LA* *Studium Biblicum Franciscanum Liber Annuus*
- LRBC* e.g., P.V. Hill and J.P.C. Kent. Part 1: The Bronze Coinage of the House of Constantine, A.D. 324–46. In *Late Roman Bronze Coinage (A.D. 324–498)*. London 1965. Pp. 4–40
- MIB* e.g., W. Hahn. *Von Anastasius I. bis Justinianus I (491–565)*. Moneta Imperii Byzantini 1. Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften Philosophisch-Historische Klasse Denkschriften 109. Veröffentlichungen der Numismatischen Kommission 1. Vienna 1973
- MIBE* W. Hahn. *Money of the Incipient Byzantine Empire (Anastasius I–Justinian I, 491–565)* (Veröffentlichungen des Instituts für Numismatik und Geldgeschichte der Universität Wien 6). Vienna 2000
- MIBEC* W. Hahn and M. Metlich. *Money of the Incipient Byzantine Empire Continued (Justin II—Revolt of the Heraclii, 565–610)*. (Veröffentlichungen des Instituts für Numismatik und Geldgeschichte der Universität Wien 13). Vienna 2009
- MN* *American Numismatic Society Museum Notes*
- NC* *Numismatic Chronicle*
- NCirc.* *Numismatic Circular*
- NNM* *Numismatic Notes and Monographs*
- RIC* e.g., C.H.V. Sutherland. *The Roman Imperial Coinage I. From 31 BC to AD 69*. London 1984
- RN* *Revue Numismatique*
- RPC* e.g., A. Burnett, M. Amandry and I. Carradice. *From Vespasian to Domitian (AD 69–96)*. *Roman Provincial Coinage 2*. London 1999
- RRC* M.H. Crawford. *Roman Republican Coinage*. Cambridge 1974
- SC* e.g., A. Houghton and C. Lorber. *Seleucid Coins. A Comprehensive Catalogue. Part I. Seleucus I through Antiochus III*. New York, Lancaster, Penn.-London 2002
- SICA* e.g., S. Album and T. Goodwin. *Sylloge of Islamic Coins in the Ashmolean 1: The Pre-Reform Coinage of the Early Islamic Period*. Oxford 2002
- SNAT* e.g., L. Ilisch. *Sylloge Numorum Arabicorum Tübingen–Palästina IVa Bilād aš-Šām I*. Tübingen 1993
- SNG* *Sylloge Nummorum Graecorum* (with suffix as necessary, e.g. *SNG Cop.*)
- SNR* *Schweizerische Numismatische Rundschau*
- TINC* *Transactions of the International Numismatic Congress*
- TJC* Y. Meshorer. *A Treasury of Jewish Coins from the Persian Period to Bar Kochba*. Jerusalem-Nyack 2001
- ZfN* *Zeitschrift für Numismatik*